

Do quaternary methyls ($-N^+(\text{CH}_3)_3$) behave differently from alkyl methyls ($\text{R}-\text{CH}_3$) in aqueous media?

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Abstract : Methyl groups attached with quaternary nitrogen ($-N^+(\text{CH}_3)_3$; denoted as quaternary methyl) are widespread in chemical and biological systems in the form of surfactants, biological membranes, osmolytes, etc. Unlike alkyl methyl (i.e. methyl attached with alkyl group, $\text{R}-\text{CH}_3$), the positively charged nitrogen is believed to polarize the C-H bonds of quaternary methyls so that the latter behave more like a polar hydrophilic group while interacting with water. By vibrational probing of alkyl- and quaternary-methyls (e.g. *tert*-butyl alcohol, TBA and trimethylamine N-oxide, TMAO) in D_2O and CDCl_3 , we provide direct experimental evidence that the mode of interactions of these two types of methyls (with water and nonpolar molecules) are quite similar to each other. Both $\text{R}-\text{CH}_3$ and N^+-CH_3 exhibit blue-shifted H-bonding with water, revealing their apolar character. Furthermore, we have probed the interaction of these methyls in the hydration shell of ions, by selectively extracting the vibrational spectrum of TMAO/TBA pertinent to the hydration shell of halide ions using Raman multivariate curve resolution (Raman-MCR) spectroscopy. The MCR-retrieved spectra also reveal that both alkyl and quaternary methyls are less interacting with hydration water than that with bulk water. Together, these results suggest that the positive charge on the nitrogen, though polarize the C-H bonds of quaternary methyls to some extent, does not enable them to behave like a typical polar vibrational chromophore.

Keywords : Raman spectroscopy, multivariate curve resolution, hydration shell, trimethylamine N-oxide, osmolyte, hydrophilic and hydrophobic.

Introduction

Interactions among hydrophobic molecular groups, ions, and water play important roles in various chemical and biological processes including folding-unfolding of proteins, formation of lipid bilayer membranes, adsorption/desorption of metabolites and foreign molecules (e.g. drug) on cell surface, etc.¹⁻⁵. It has been found that small hydrophobic groups such as the methyl group of methanol promote stronger (than bulk water) H-bonding among vicinal water molecules (hydrophobic hydration)^{6,7} and ions of varying charge density are either adsorbed or depleted from the hydrophobic molecular surface^{8,9}. However, in various chemical and biological systems, methyl groups appear not only as uncharged alkyl group, but also as methylammonium cation.

For example, methyl groups attached with a positively charged nitrogen ($-N^+(\text{CH}_3)_3$; Fig. 1A) occurs in the headgroup of biological membranes and osmolytes. Unlike the alkyl methyls ($\text{R}-\text{CH}_3$), the apolar nature of quaternary methyl ($-N^+(\text{CH}_3)_3$) as well as its mode of interaction with ions/water are debatable^{10,11}.

Thermodynamic studies suggested that quaternary methyls do not show hydrophobicity rather promote hydrophilicity¹². Vibrational sum frequency generation (VSFG) study¹¹ of TMAO at the octadecyltrichlorosilane (OTS)/water interface showed that the quaternary methyls of TMAO prefer the aqueous phase than the hydrophobic alkyl phase of OTS, indicating the hydrophilic nature of quaternary methyls. Infrared study and theoretical calculation of

Fig. 1. (A) Chemical structure of prototype molecules containing alkyl methyls (TBA) and quaternary methyls (TMAO and TMA). (B) Motivation (schematic) : Interaction of a methyl group and water has been probed by measuring the methyl C-H stretch vibration (Raman band).

methylphosphatidylcholine (mimic of the phosphatidylcholine lipid headgroup) indicated that at low hydration level, the choline-methyls (methyls with quaternary nitrogen) participate in red-shifted H-bond interaction with the phosphate group¹³. This means the positively charged nitrogen of phosphatidylcholine makes the C-H bonds of the quaternary methyls polar enough to participate in conventional red-shifted H-bond interaction with anionic phosphate group. On the other hand, heterodyne-detected-VSFG study¹⁴ at the phosphatidylcholine lipid/water interfaces proposed that the choline group provide a hydrophobic environment to the neighboring water molecules, which is in agreement with other theoretical studies as well^{15,16}. Accordingly, one would expect that the methyl groups attached with the choline nitrogen behaves like a nonpolar group. Very recently, using HD-VSFG spectroscopy which can directly reveal the absolute orientation of a molecule at an interface, we have shown that the quaternary methyls of TMAO are oriented away from the aqueous phase (i.e. towards the air) at the air-water interface¹⁷. This preferential orientation of quaternary methyl (TMAO) is similar to that of alkyl methyl (TBA) at the air-water interface¹⁰. Thus the HD-VSFG studies^{10,17}, contrary to the conventional VSFG study¹¹, suggest apolar character for quaternary methyls.

The hydrophilic nature of quaternary methyls as indicated by the conventional VSFG study¹¹ or the

hydrophobic nature, as suggested by the HD-VSFG studies^{10,14,17}, were indirectly inferred either from the preferential orientation of TMAO-methyls at the OTS/water or air-water interfaces or from the structure of water at the vicinity of the choline at the PC/water interface. For the unambiguous assignment of the polar (or apolar) nature of quaternary methyls, it is essential to directly probe the mode of interaction of quaternary methyls with water, and compare the result with typical polar (say, $>C=O$) and apolar alkyl methyl groups.

In this paper, we measured the CH_3 stretch bands of TBA, acetone and TMAO in nonpolar $CDCl_3$ and polar D_2O solvents (deuterated solvents were used to avoid spectral interference of solvent in the CH stretch region). We have also compared the mode of interaction of quaternary and alkyl methyls in the hydration shell of halide ions using Raman-MCR spectroscopy. Raman-MCR is a powerful spectroscopic technique which can extract the otherwise difficult to obtain vibrational signature of molecules in the solvation shell of a solute; and has been widely used by us¹⁸⁻²⁰ and others²¹⁻²³. Our results show that the nature of interaction of quaternary methyl in the hydration shell of halide ions is also similar to that of alkyl methyl, though the positive charge on the quaternary nitrogen brings the water molecules closer to the nitrogen atom, leading to stronger interaction with quaternary methyl than that with the alkyl methyls.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

The chemicals, trimethylamine-N-oxide dihydrate (TMAO, $\geq 99.0\%$), tetramethylammonium chloride (TMA) ($\geq 98.0\%$), and heavy water (D_2O , > 99.9 atom % D) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. *tert*-Butanol and acetone (99.5%, HPLC grade) were from Spectrochem India. $CDCl_3$ (99.8%, NMR grade), and potassium halide salts ($\geq 99.0\%$) were from Merck. All the chemicals were used as received. Milli-Q water (18.2 M Ω cm resistivity) was used for the measurements. The unpolarized Raman spectra were recorded at 23°C using a micro-Raman spectrometer (SEKI Technotron, Japan). Low concentra-

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tions of solutes ($\leq 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) were used to ensure that the solutes are fully-hydrated without appreciable solute-solute interactions (e.g. aggregation or ion pairing). Samples in a quartz cell of 2 mm optical path length were excited at 532 nm (power $\sim 20 \text{ mW}$ at sample position) using a 10X objective lens (Olympus). The scattered light was collected by the same objective lens and passed through an edge filter (LPO3-532RU-25) to filter Rayleigh and anti-Stokes scattered signals. The Stokes signal after the edge filter was passed through a fiber-coupled spectrograph (Acton series SP 2300i, 1200 groove/mm) and detected by a thermo-electric cooled (-75°C) charge-coupled device (CCD, Model no. PIXIS : 256). For polarized (isotropic and anisotropic) Raman measurements, the parallel ($I_{||}$) and perpendicular (I_{\perp}) spectra were obtained by placing a laminated film polarizer (Thorlabs) in front of the collection optical fiber. Then the isotropic (I_{iso}) and anisotropic (I_{aniso}) Raman spectra were calculated as²⁴ (I_{iso}) = $(I_{||} - \frac{4}{3} I_{\perp})$ and (I_{aniso}) = $\frac{4}{3} I_{\perp}$. The spectrograph was calibrated using the 520.5 cm^{-1} line from silicon wafer and was verified by measuring the Raman spectrum of naphthalene. The Raman spectra of all solutions were acquired under similar experimental conditions (acquisition time for each spectrum was 300 s ($60 \text{ s} \times 5$), slit width $80 \mu\text{m}$).

The experimental Raman spectra of the aqueous solution (e.g. aqueous TBA solution in presence of NaCl, contain the vibrational response of the TBA in bulk water and in the hydration shell of Na^+ and Cl^- ions). In diluted NaCl solution ($\sim 1.0 \text{ M}$), the relative contribution of hydration shell TBA (i.e. the vibrational response for those TBA located in the hydration shell of the ions) is negligibly small compared to that of bulk TBA (i.e. TBA located in the bulk water). As a result, in diluted solution, the weak spectral response of hydration shell TBA gets concealed in the strong signal of bulk TBA. It is to be noted that one should not use high concentration of salt (NaCl) which may lead to shearing of hydration shell and ion-pairing which will complicate the interpretation of the subtle spectral changes pertinent to the hydration shell. Multivariate curve resolution

analysis of the Raman spectra of aqueous TBA solutions “with” and “without” NaCl provides the vibrational spectrum of TBA pertinent to the hydration shell of Cl^- ion. Unlike in conventional difference spectroscopy and peak fitting, MCR analysis does not have any assumption about the amplitude, position, and width of spectral bands, making it a robust technique for solvation spectroscopy²⁵.

Before the multivariate analysis of the experimentally recorded spectra, we have subtracted a constant background from the experimental spectra so that there are zero signals in the spectral region beyond the vibrational resonance. At least, two such background subtracted spectra were averaged, and then the averaged spectrum was smoothed by 2nd order Savitzky-Golay algorithm with 19 points. We note that the smoothing operation while reducing noise in the spectrum did not produce any noticeable change in the Raman bands.

The smoothed Raman spectra were area normalized to nullify the effect of intensity variation (either due to laser fluctuation or due to the change in Raman cross-section of water in presence of solutes). The area normalized Raman spectra were arranged into the rows of a matrix (the first row of the matrix is the reference spectrum without the ion hydration shells i.e. the spectrum of TBA solution without NaCl) for multivariate analysis. In the MCR analysis, first the data matrix was decomposed by singular value decomposition (SVD) that provided information about the number of significant spectral components and their spectral responses. These initial estimates were optimized by alternating least square (ALS) fitting method. One of the two spectral components, obtained after SVD-ALS operations, represents the response of bulk TBA, and the other component corresponds to the response of hydration shell TBA, which is designated as ion-correlated spectra (IC-spectra).

Results and discussion

Vibrational solvatochromism of alkyl and quaternary methyls :

Fig. 1 shows the Raman spectra (CH stretch) of

TBA (specimen of R-CH₃) and TMAO (specimen of N⁺-CH₃) in CDCl₃ (nonpolar aprotic) and D₂O (polar protic). The CH stretch bands of TBA are overlapped with each other in 2850–3000 cm⁻¹ region, whereas TMAO shows two well resolved bands – one at around 3030 cm⁻¹ and the other at around 2970 cm⁻¹. The symmetry of the Raman active mode of TBA are revealed by the depolarization ratio (ρ) shown by the dotted curve in Fig. 2a ($\rho = I_{\perp}/I_{\parallel}$; where I_{\perp} and I_{\parallel} are the perpendicular and parallel component of Raman intensity, see Experimental Section). The 2972 cm⁻¹ band of TBA has a ρ value equals to 0.75, whereas the bands below 2960 cm⁻¹ (2938 cm⁻¹, 2910 cm⁻¹, 2860 cm⁻¹) have the ρ values less than 0.1. For a totally symmetric vibrational mode, ρ is less than 0.75 (polarized band); and for an anti-symmetric vibration, ρ equals to 0.75 (depolarized band)²⁶. Accordingly, the 2860 and 2972 cm⁻¹ bands of TBA (in CDCl₃) correspond to the symmetric and antisymmetric CH₃ stretch (CH₃^{SS} and CH₃^{AS}), respectively. The in-between bands at 2910 and 2938 cm⁻¹ are due to Fermi resonance between CH₃ stretch and bend overtones²⁷. On changing the solvent from nonpolar CDCl₃ to polar D₂O, the symmetric and anti-symmetric CH₃ stretch bands of TBA are shifted towards higher frequency by ~ 7 cm⁻¹ (blue-shift; $\nu(\text{CH}_3^{\text{SS}}) = 2867$ cm⁻¹ and $\nu(\text{CH}_3^{\text{AS}}) = 2979$ cm⁻¹). The blue-shift indicates that the C-H bonds of the alkyl methyl of TBA (R-CH₃) become shorter and stronger in D₂O than that in CDCl₃. Previous experimental and computational studies^{28–31} suggested that the vibrational frequency of a typical covalent bond, A-H, red-shifts due to hydrogen-bond interaction when the A-H bond is polar in character (conventional H-bonding); and blue-shifts when the A-H bond is nonpolar (unconventional H-bonding). This is because a polar A-H bond becomes weaker due to the H-bonding interaction with B (A-H---B). Whereas, a nonpolar A-H bond becomes shorter and stronger due to the displacement of A-H bond-electrons towards 'A' caused by repulsive interaction with the lone-pairs (or negative charge) of B³². Thus, the 7 cm⁻¹ blue-shift for TBA is consistent with the nonpolar nature of the C-H bonds of the alkyl methyls.

In the case of TMAO, the ρ value of the 3020 cm⁻¹ band is ~ 0.75 and that for the bands below 2985 cm⁻¹ is less than 0.1, indicating their anti-symmetric and symmetric natures, respectively³³. Since the methyls are attached with electron withdrawing positively charged nitrogen in TMAO, it is expected that the C-H bonds (of TMAO) will be shorter and stronger than that of TBA. This is reflected in the frequency position of the CH₃^{SS} and CH₃^{AS} bands of TMAO, which are ~ 80 and 50 cm⁻¹ blue-shifted than those of TBA $\nu(\text{CH}_3^{\text{SS}}, \text{TMAO}) = 2940$ cm⁻¹ and $\nu(\text{CH}_3^{\text{AS}}, \text{TMAO}) = 3020$ cm⁻¹ in CDCl₃. Thus quaternary methyls (as in TMAO) have stronger C-H bonds than that of alkyl methyl (as in TBA). However, the question remains, does such electron withdrawal by the positively charged nitrogen make the attached methyls polar enough, so that their nature of interaction with water and ions becomes different from the alkyl methyls? As can be seen from Fig. 2B, the CH-stretch bands of TMAO are also blue-shifted by ~ 12 – 15 cm⁻¹ in D₂O from that in CDCl₃. The blue-shift indicates that the quaternary methyls of TMAO interact with water via the unconventional blue-shifted H-bonding. In other words, the positive charge on the nitrogen of TMAO, though makes the C-H bonds shorter and stronger, does not change the nonpolar character of its methyls. Nevertheless, the higher magnitude of the blue-shift (~ 13 cm⁻¹ for TMAO vs ~ 7 cm⁻¹ for TBA) indicates larger bond contraction for quaternary methyls due to closer approach of water towards TMAO-methyls by ion-dipole interaction³².

To further illustrate the vibrational solvatochromism of R-CH₃ and N⁺-CH₃ with reference to that of a polar vibrational chromophore (e.g. the carbonyl group, >C=O), we have plotted the spectral shift of the >C=O stretch of acetone against the E_{T}^{N} values of solvents (Fig. 3; E_{T}^{N} is the normalized version of the E_{T} (30) scale of polarity). As expected, the polar >C=O group red-shifts with increasing E_{T}^{N} values, making a negative curvature in the ν/ν_0 vs E_{T}^{N} plot (ν is the vibrational band position in a sol-

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Fig. 2. Raman spectra of (A) TBA and (B) TMAO in apolar CDCl_3 (dashed curve) and polar D_2O (solid curves) in the CH stretch regions. The spectra are normalized at the high frequency CH stretch band. Concentration of TBA is 0.01 mole fraction in D_2O and CDCl_3 , whereas that of TMAO is 0.01 mole fraction in D_2O , but less in CDCl_3 , since TMAO is only weakly soluble in nonpolar CDCl_3 .

vent and ν_0 is the band position in apolar CDCl_3). The methyl groups of acetone shows a positive curvature, revealing their apolar nature. The response of TBA-methyls are very similar to that of the acetone-methyls (Fig. 3). The TMAO-methyls too show positive curvature with E_T^N values, revealing the apolar nature of the quaternary methyls. However, the extent of the solvatochromic shift is larger than that of TBA or acetone due to stronger interaction of $N^+-\text{CH}_3$ with water than that of $\text{R}-\text{CH}_3$.

Fig. 3. Plot of relative position of Raman bands (ν/ν_0 ; ν is the vibrational band position in different solvents and ν_0 is the band position in apolar CDCl_3) vs E_T^N values for the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretch of acetone (\bullet) and CH_3^{AS} of acetone (\blacksquare), TBA (\boxtimes) and TMAO (\circ). The dashed lines are a guide to eye for the variation of ν/ν_0 .

Vibrational mapping of alkyl and quaternary methyls in the hydration shell of halide ions :

To understand the interaction of the alkyl (TBA) and quaternary methyls (TMAO and TMA^+) with halide ions, we have retrieved the CH-stretch bands of the respective methyls in the hydration shell of different halide ions (F^- , Cl^- , Br^- and I^-) using Raman-MCR spectroscopy. Since, we used the halide salts of a common cation (Na^+), the relative spectral changes in the MCR-retrieved spectra can be attributed to the halide ions. Moreover, low concentration of NaX ($\sim 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was used to minimize the ‘indirect ion-effect’ on the CH-stretch bands. ‘Indirect ion-effect’ means the ionic perturbation of long-range structure of water and the subsequent effect of the ‘perturbed-water’ on the vibrational response the methyls. At such low concentration of salt, the experimental Raman spectra, exhibit little change in the CH-stretch bands (see Fig. 4A, 4C and 4E). However, by applying MCR analysis on the apparently similar experimental Raman spectra, we have selectively extracted the vibrational response of ion-affected methyls (ion correlated spectra (IC-spectra), Fig. 4). The CH-stretch band of IC-spectrum is $\sim 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ red-shifted of TBA in the hydration shell of I^- (for other halide ions the changes are not significant). the red-shift (of TBA-methyls in

the hydration shell of I^-) reveals that the methyls are less exposed to water in the hydration shell of I^- than that in bulk water³⁴. The negligible effect of other halide ions (F^- , Cl^- , Br^-) on the CH -stretch bands of TBA could be due to the depletion of TBA in the hydration shell of halide ions as suggested by recent Raman-MCR studies^{9,35}.

In the case of TMAO, the frequency position of the IC-spectra (Fig. 4D) are more red-shifted than that of TBA, and the red-shift increases with increasing polarizability of the halide ions. Similar results have been obtained for the IC-spectra of TMA^+

as shown in Fig. 4F. A plot of the frequency shift of the CH_3^{AS} band of TBA, TMAO and TMA^+ corresponding to different anions are shown in Fig. 5. The plots show a negative slope for both $R-CH_3$ and N^+-CH_3 ($TMAO$ and TMA^+) with increasing size of the halide ions. This suggests that similar to alkyl methyls (TBA), quaternary methyls ($TMAO$ and TMA^+) are also “less exposed” to water in the hydration shell of halide ions. Alternatively, one can also argue that the H-bond strength of water in the hydration shell (primary) of halide ions decreases as the size of the halide ions increases^{18,19}. Because of weaker H-bonding; the O-H bonds of ‘hydration-water’ are less polarized than that of bulk water. The less polarized O-H bonds, in turn, make the oxygen of hydration-water (O_{HW}) a weaker electron donor compared to that of bulk water (O_{BW})^{31,32}. Thus, in the hydration shell of halide

Fig. 4. Raman spectra of the CH_3 stretch bands of (A) TBA, (C) TMAO and (E) TMAOI in presence of Na-halide (1.0 mol dm^{-3}) in D_2O . MCR-retrieved halide ion-correlated CH_3 stretch bands of (B) TBA, (D) TMAO and (F) TMA^+ in D_2O . Concentration of TBA, TMAO and TMAOI is 1.0 mol dm^{-3} for each. The experimental Raman spectra and the ion-correlated spectra are presented after normalizing at their respective CH_3^{AS} band. TMA^+ precipitates in presence of NaI ($\geq 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and hence, the Raman spectra of TMA^+ could not recorded in presence of NaI .

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Fig. 5. Peak-shift of the CH_3^{AS} bands of TBA (\bullet), TMAO (Δ) and TMA^+ (\square) in the hydration shell of different halide ions.

ions (except F^-), the methyls of $\text{R-CH}_3/\text{N}^+-\text{CH}_3$ are exposed to water whose electron donating ability decreases progressively as the size of the halide ions increases. As a result, the magnitude of the red-shift of the CH_3 -stretch bands of TMAO increase as the size of the halide ions increases. Thus, it is obvious that the interactions of quaternary methyls with ions and water are similar in nature to those of alkyl-methyl. However, the magnitude of the slope is larger for N^+-CH_3 than R-CH_3 . Moreover, the onset of the red-shift starts with Cl^- anion for TBA, but with F^- anion for TMAO, indicating higher sensitivity of quaternary methyl towards halide ions than that of alkyl methyls. This is due to electrostatic attraction of the negatively charged halide ions with the positively charged nitrogen of TMAO/TMA⁺. Thus, from water's perspective the R-CH_3 and N^+-CH_3 groups are similar in nature and provide an apolar environment to adjacent water molecules.

Conclusions

Alkyl and quaternary methyls (R-CH_3 and N^+-CH_3) are widespread in nature and play critical roles in various biological processes and applied fields. The present investigation provides site specific information about the nature of interaction of these methyls with ions and water. It is observed that the nature of interaction of quaternary methyl (as in TMAO and TMA^+) is very similar to that of alkyl

methyl (as in TBA). Both alkyl and quaternary methyls undergo blue-shifted H-bond interaction with water, revealing their apolar nature. Raman-MCR spectroscopy of alkyl and quaternary methyls in presence of alkali halides in water reveals that the nature of interaction of quaternary methyl in the hydration shell of halide ions is also similar to that of alkyl methyl; both of them are less interacting with hydration water than bulk water. Thus, these results suggest that the positive charge on quaternary nitrogen cannot polarize the C-H bonds enough so that their nature of interaction with water becomes similar to that of a polar hydrophilic group. However, because of the positive charge associated with quaternary methyls, the water molecules approach closer to quaternary methyls than that of the alkyl methyls making the quaternary methyls more strongly interacting with water than that of alkyl methyls. We believe that the present study will be useful in elucidating the molecular level interaction of ions and water with osmolytes and phosphatidylcholine lipid headgroup at the membrane/water interfaces.

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